

COREnext shows the way to a safe digital future

16.07.2024 | corenext.eu

"In COREnext, we believe that **trust among the public can only be achieved if the system itself has native built-in security measures** across all implementation layers and data flows, thus forming a trustworthy-by-design platform. Whether it guarantees safety when using self-driving cars, allowing your home to blend with the metaverse, or simply preserving privacy despite connected cameras everywhere – it does not matter. The system must earn consumer's trust."

COREnext Team

["TRUSTWORTHINESS. THE KEY TO EUROPE'S DIGITAL FUTURE"](#)

[1st Year of the project in a nutshell](#)

Europe is leading digital innovation with COREnext, a pioneering initiative celebrating its first-year anniversary. COREnext is dedicated to anticipating technological advancements for future 6G networks.

[COREnext spotted at EUCNC 2024](#)

At EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024, Fredrik Tillman from Ericsson and Zulaicha Parastuty from Infineon Technologies presented the COREnext White Paper.

[COREnext Releases White Paper: Trustworthiness – The Key to Europe's Digital Future](#)

COREnext, a EU-funded project focused on advancing Europe's digital infrastructure, released its latest white paper, "Trustworthiness – The Key to Europe's Digital Future." This comprehensive study examines the critical role of trust and security in the digitalisation process, underscoring the essential steps needed to maintain Europe's leadership in high-end consumer goods.

[Download the White Paper here!](#)

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[COREnext Cyber Security Campaign 2023: Unveiling the Growing Threats Across Industries](#)

In an era dominated by technology, the manufacturing industry finds itself at the forefront of an escalating wave of cyber threats. Recent research sheds light on the most pressing concerns facing the sector in the first half of 2023. Here's an overview of some key findings and a few recommendations to navigate the complex cyber landscape.

[Understanding Trustworthiness in the COREnext Platform: Security Aspects](#)

Trustworthiness is a critical component in any service, and its importance is magnified in the context of the COREnext platform. To comprehend its significance, a deep understanding of potential adversaries seeking to exploit vulnerabilities is crucial.

[A Deep Dive into Attacker Models, From Network-Based Strikes to Application-Based Intricacies](#)

In the ever-evolving landscape of cybersecurity, understanding the intricacies of potential threats is paramount. This article serves as an exploration into the description of primary attacker models.

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CORENEXT is an EU-funded (Horizon Europe – Grant Agreement number 101092598) initiative that will bring together expert stakeholders in future mobile networks and integrate their perspectives in key focus areas like digital, analogue, and integrated solutions for computing, communication, and sensing.

[Learn more](#)

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